

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES AND WORD-BUILDING POTENTIAL OF ENGLISH ADVERBIAL SUFFIX *-LY* AND ITS TAJIK EQUIVALENTS

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Abstract. *The article dwells on the issues beset with the comparative analysis of word-building potential of English adverbial suffix -ly and its Tajik equivalents. It is underscored that the lexical fields of adverbs are very broad and their functional types are different. It is concluded that adverbs are divided into simple, derivative, compound and composite groups based on their structure in the comparative languages and depending on their meaning they are singled out into the following sub-groups, such as: place, time, direction, frequency, modal (English), cause and purpose, manner of action and quantity and degree. Hereby, we can canvass those Tajik equivalents of English derivative adverbs of formed by this suffix are not identical and the same-formed ones, and some of them are used and translated as simple, derivative, compound & mix structural and composite ones.*

Keywords: *adverb, comparative analysis, adverbs, English and Tajik languages, simple, derivative, compound and composite adverbs.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada ingliz tilidagi -ly qo'shimchasi va uning tojikcha ekvivalentlarining so'z yasash imkoniyatlarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish masalalariga to'xtalib o'tiladi. Qo'shimchalarning lug'aviy sohalari juda keng bo'lib, funksional turlari har xil ekanligi ta'kidlanadi. Xulosa qilinadiki, qo'shimchalar qiyosiy tillarda tuzilishiga ko'ra sodda, hosila, qo'shma va qo'shma guruhlarga bo'linadi va ma'nosiga ko'ra quyidagi kichik guruhlarga ajratiladi: o'rin, vaqt, yo'nalish, chastota, modal (inglizcha), sabab va maqsad, harakat tarzi va miqdor va daraja. Bu orqali ingliz tilidagi hosila qo'shimchalarining tojikcha ekvivalentlari o'xshash va bir xil shaklli emasligini va ularning ba'zilar sodda, hosila, qo'shma va aralash strukturaviy va qo'shma shakllarda qo'llanib, tarjima qilinganini ko'rib chiqishimiz mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ergash gap, qiyosiy tahlil, ergash gaplar, ingliz va tojik tillari, sodda, hosila, qo'shma va qo'shma ergash gaplar.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются вопросы сравнительного анализа словообразовательного потенциала английского наречного суффикса -ly и его таджикских эквивалентов. Подчеркивается, что лексические поля наречий очень широки и их функциональные типы различны. Сделан вывод о том, что наречия по структуре в компаративных языках делятся на простые, производные, составные и сложные группы и в зависимости от значения выделяются на следующие подгруппы, такие как: место, время, направление, частотность, модальное (английское), причина и цель, способ действия, количество и степень. Таким образом, мы можем выявить те таджикские эквиваленты английских производных наречий, образованных этим суффиксом, которые не являются тождественными и однообразными, а некоторые из них употребляются и переводятся как простые, производные, составные и смешанные структурные и составные.*

Ключевые слова: наречие, сопоставительный анализ, наречия, английский и таджикский языки, простые, производные, сложные и составные наречия.

Introduction

Commonly, “the subject of language typology includes all the systems of the world’s famous languages and the relevant field is considered to be as a part of general linguistic studies. Therefore, a series of factological materials and proved evidence targeted at the comparative study of near and foreign languages is one of the natural branches of linguistic typology. There is a difference between typological and comparative studies of languages - both in terms of the linguistic research method: in comparative research they use the deductive method, and in terms of typology - the inductive method is used” [16, p.120; 12, p.257].

It is worth stressing that one of the issues dealing with grammatical and morphological categories of adverb in both Tajik and English languages is the key one in today`s linguistics studies under the angle of comparative aspect. Hence, adverb is considered to be one of the independent parts of speech, which the relevant linguistic unit is backgrounded later than other parts of speech in the languages under comparison. As well as, the part of speech in question is introduced in details and is included into the program targeted at higher educational establishments. Iranian linguists have also paid particular attention to the exploration and consideration of adverb. In conformity with Ali Muhammad Furughi`s opinion, this part of speech is a linguistic unit that is resorted to differentiate and reveal the content of verb, adjective or any other adverb [15, p.132].

As well as, D.S. Phillot devoted a section of his work to adverbs and adverbial phrases and he explained in detail the ways and means of the derivation of adverbs and adverbial composition and phrases. He noted that “auxiliary adverbial one is a participle used as an adverb, the noun of an adverb can be a noun instead of the former in question” and he considered adverbs and adverbial phrases the relevant part of speech as any words and phrases, even separate sentences [14, p.495-487].

Into the bargain, “original adverbs” the usage of nouns and adjectives and certain pronouns and Arabic words and phrases as adverbs; the derivation of adverbs by dint of suffixes has also been canvassed by G.K. Zaleman [7, p.65-67].

Under the angle of a famous scholar in linguistic studies - E.E. Bertels one can assert that “while forming the part speech in question (in Persian) transfers from adjectives to adverb without any changing its form by dint of the nominal parts with the suffix *-ona* and adverbization of Arabic words (by means of the suffix *-an*) as well” [4, p.75-79].

In reference to it, Yu.A. Rubinchik has adduced detailed information concerned with sematico-grammatical peculiarities of Tajik adverbs, on its difference from modal words and adverbs derivation by means of the affixes *ba-*, *-i*, *-aki*, prepositions and nominal parts and various words repetition, in particular [11, p.92].

Book Review

While conducting the contrastive analysis, we have resorted to the following works, literary productions and bilingual dictionary as reliable sources, including: “Ghulomon” by S.Aini (2019) [1]; “Lughat-i anglisi-tojiki” by A.Mamadnazarov (2011) [10]; “A Book of Golden Deeds” by Jim Manis (2004) [17] and “Lughat-i muxtasri kalimasozii zaboni adabii tojik” (1983) [5]. These sources are of great importance and contribute the key role in the development of comparative linguistics studies.

The objectives of the article under consideration are: to carry out distinctive peculiarities of some derivative adverbs morphologically; to reveal the significance of the above-mentioned reliable sources theoretically and scientifically; to compare the place and role of word-building elements forming a series of adverbs in the comparative languages; to dwell on certain urgent issues beset with the theme explored in details.

Methodology

While canvassing the distinctive peculiarities and the level of usage of the prefixes under study, we have resorted the following visual methods, such as: comparative-historical, synchronic-diachronic ones.

Main results and discussion

The majority of simple adverbs of the comparative languages are of the long history and they possess specific functions and particular features, upon the whole. Affixation is very productive in adverbial word-derivation in the comparative languages. By dint of prefixes and suffixes a large considerable number of new adverbs of manner are formed from various parts of speech, namely *noun, adjective, verb bases* we will reveal their certain morphological and semantical features in terms of comparative aspects. The derivation of adverbs by means of affixes is considered to be one of the most common and productive ways of word-building, and all independent parts of speech possess such kind of potentiality in the languages under comparison. In reference to it, affixes occupy an important role in the word-building potential and involve in the formation of adverbs, but they are shared between adverbs and adjectives as well.

There are a number of affixes in the comparative languages: Tajik word-building elements *prefixes: be-, no-, ba-, bo-, bar-, dar-, to-* and the following traditional Tajik adverbial suffixes still occupy an important role, including: *-aki, -o, -ona, -vor, -noki, -son, -i (-gi) and -an* [6: 275] and prefixes English: *im-, un-, non-, mis-, dis-* suffixes: *-ly, -wards, -wise, -ically* and only *in-* is a prefix denoting the place.

Hereby, we will focus on comparative analysis of morphological peculiarities and the level of usage of certain derivative adverbs in English and Tajik languages.

It is well-grounded that adverbs of both languages are divided into simple, derivative, compound and composite morphologically. Factual material of the comparative languages like Tajik language: *zud, soz, sahl, aknun, fardo, peš, der, por, di, dūš, edar, edūš, hameša, hanūz, bisyor, allakai* one-rooted words are included in simple adverbs and like English: *very – xele, fast – tex, here – injo, why – baroi či, always – hameša* [2; 3; 13]. For instance:

I don't realize the fact that *why* we must tell them about her – Man namefahmam, ki *čaro* mo boyad ba onho dar bora-i ū naql kunem [Translated by the author].

...ba šarofat-i janob-i oli amir-i Bukhoro-i šarif dar *in jo* bo osudagi zindagi mekuned [1, p.200]- ...owing to His Excellency - the Emir of Bukhara, you live *here* comfortably [Translated by the author];

Aknun *dar kujo* budanam va *kujo* raftanam-ro durust pay naburdam [1, p.317] - Now I didn't know *where* I have been and *where* I was going to [Translated by the author].

Adducing the results of the above-mentioned examples one can assert that the equivalents of simple adverbs of EL into Tajik are various ones, because *here (simple) = in jo (composite) and where (simple) = dar kujo (composite)* morphologically.

The majority of English adverbs are derivated by virtue of the adverbial suffix *-ly*. It is worth stressing the formation of adverbs from different parts of speech is considered to be one of the main and most productive ways of adverb derivation or word-building in the comparative

languages [3; 4; 16]. We can confidently express our opinion that the usage of parts of speech in adverb derivation is not identical in Tajik and English languages. Adjectives are more frequently used in the formation of adverbs than other parts of speech in the languages being compared. Hereby, we decided to single out certain English derivative adverbs into sub-groups based on various parts of speech + the adverbial suffix *-ly* and to dwell on distinctive and common peculiarities in term of structure:

a) **based on noun + the adverbial suffix *-ly***: name – *namely* (asosan, ya`ne), man – *manly* (odamvor, insoniyona), friend – *friendly* (dūstona, rafiqona, boiltifot), brother – *brotherly* (barodarona), sister – *sisterly* (xoharona), master – *masterly* (jobukona, mohirona): Xanda nakuneton, -guft agrotexnik, *-asosan fikr-i in rafiq durust ast* [1, p.449] - My dear, I must leave you, *that is* my only regret, except that I could not restore my king to the throne; I leave you in the midst of a civil war, *that is* what afflicts me [17, p.254].

While adducing and collecting the appropriate examples and facts we didn't find the English equivalent of *namely* in "A Book of Golden Deeds" by Jim Manis (2004) [17], but J.Manis had resorted to *that is* very much as a synonym of the above-mentioned English derivative adverb in his book.

b) **based on adjective + the adverbial suffix *-ly***: serious - *seriously* (jiddi, aniq), happy – *happily* (xušbaxtona, xursandona), general – *generally* (dar umum, dar majmu`, umuman, hamagi), proper – *properly* (xosatan, az jumla, bavizha), original – *originally* (aslan, dar asl), wise – *wisely* (donišmandona, xiradmandona, boaqłona), proud – *proudly* (boiftixor), honest – *honestly* (boinsofona, bovijdonona), haughty – *haughtily* (boğurur), active – *actively* (fa`olona, boğayratona), faithful – *faithfully* (bovafo): *Happily* their shout was heard by a man of different mould [17: 222], Sodiq az xona baromada ba taraf-i kohxona raft, zanak *xursandona* ba sar-i otašdon nigoh karda davida raft, ba ošpazi daromad va bačagonaš, ki az kūča omadand, bo jūšu xurūši bačagona tractor-ro ta`rif karda xursandii ū-ro meafzudand... [1, p.405], He *actively* and *dexterously* took part in all manly sports, espe-cially shooting and riding [17, p.245], Aknun lozim meoyad, ki in kas az šumo ziyodtar haq girand-diya –guft javon-i yakdasta, ki az taraf-i boy Yuldošev xitob yofta bud, *pičiigomezona* ba boy... [1, p.396].

c) **based on numeral + the adverbial suffix *-ly***: first – *firstly* (naxust, avvalan, dar avval), second – *secondly* (soniyan, ba`dan), third - *thirdly* (seyuman, seyum marotiba): *Firstly*, I want to tell you about this grammatical feature, *secondly*, I will dwell on its common and deferent aspects, *thirdly*, I can come to the certain conclusion - *Avvalan*, mexoham dar bora-i in xususiyat-i grammatiki naql namoyam, *soniyan*, jihatho-i umumi va farqunanda-i on-ro barrasi mekunam, *ba`dan*, ba yak xulosa-i aniq omada metavonam [translated by the author].

d) **based on participle I &II + the adverbial suffix *-ly***: delighted – *delightedly* (taajjubomezona, hayratomezona) devoted – *devotedly* (bovafo), well grounded – *well groundedly* (boasos), willing - *willingly* (sidqan), surprising – *surprisingly* (taajjubomezona, hayratomezona), seeming – *seemingly* (zohiran), feeling – *feelingly* (boehsosot): Miršab *taajjubkunon* sar-i xud-ro az on dariča darun karda, har taraf-i darun-i zinxona-ro az nazar guzaronid [1, p.205] – *Surprisingly*, miršab poked his head through the door and examined all sides of the saddle room [translated by the author].

Based on the above-given examples, we decided to dwell and canvass TEs (Tajik equivalents) of EDAs (English derivative adverbs) derived by virtue of the relevant prefix are not identical, namely, the majority of them are used and translated into TL (Tajik language) as simple, derivative & mix structural, compound and composite ones: **simple**: jiddi, aniq/*seriously*, naxust /

firstly, ya`ne / namely; **derivative by means of the prefixes bo-& ba-:** bavizha / properly, boiftifot / friendly, boiftixor / proudly, boğurur / haughtily, bovafo / faithfully, bovafo / devotedly, boasos / well groundedly, boehsosot / feelingly; **the suffix -an:** asosan / namely, umuman / generally, xosatan / properly, aslan / originally, avvalan / firstly, soniyan, ba`dan / secondly, seyuman / thirdly, sidqan / willingly, zohiran / seemingly; **the suffix -i (-gi):** hamagi / generally; **the suffix -ona:** insoniyona / manly, dūstona, rafiqona / friendly, barodarona / brotherly, xoharona / sisterly, jobukona, mohirona / masterly, xursandona / happily, fa`olona / actively, **the suffix -vor:** odamvor / manly; **mix structural** boaqłona / wisely, boinsofona, bovijdonona / honestly, boğayratona / actively; **compound:** xušbaxtona / happily, taajjubomezona, hayratomezona / delightedly, taajjubomezona, hayratomezona / surprisingly, xiradmandona, donišmandona / wisely; **composite:** dar umum, dar majmu` / generally, az jumla / properly, dar asl / originally, dar avval / firstly, seyum marotiba / thirdly.

In modern English literary language, there are a number of words that resemble adverbs in term of their writing or structure (by virtue of the suffix *-ly*), while they are adjectives, as follows:

brotherly – barodarona	manly – mardona
costly – arzanda	masterly – mohirona
cowardly – tarsu	motherly – modarona
deadly – margvor	neighbourly – dar hamsoyagi
elderly – solxurda	orderly – sarištakorona
fatherly – padarona	scholarly – olimona
friendly – dustona	sisterly – xoharona
lively – zindadil	timely – muosir
lonely – tanho	motherly love – modarvor dust doštan
lovely – jozibaangez	elderly people – čun odamoni solxurda

Into the bargain, EL, the following words *way*, *manner*, *fashion* participate to form new adverbs. Usually, they form series of adverbs of manner, and in Tajik language, such the formers in question are derivated by dint of the suffixes *-ona*, *-an* and *-vor*: in a friendly *way* – dūstona; in a timely *manner* – hamzamon; in an orderly *fashion* – tadrigan; in a motherly *way* – modarvor.

It should be underscored that some adverbs have two forms in EL, the first form is a simple adverb like to adjective and the other is a derivative adverb formed by means of the adverbial suffix *-ly*. Traditionally, such simple and derivative adverbs differ only in terms of meaning:

close – nazdik	closely – bodiqqat
deep – čuqur	deeply – amiqan
first – saravval	firstly – avvalan
free – roygon	freely – ozodona
hard – saxt	hardly – bazūr
last – oxirin bor	lastly – dar oxir, dar xulosa
late – der	lately – dar vaqthoi oxir
near – peši	nearly – qarib

The family only *lately* became extinct in the person of an old maiden lady [17, p.20], Too late the warnings returned upon the King's mind, and he knew it was he alone who was sought [17, p.148], Ba har hol har kore-ro, ki sar karda bošad, *der* yo *zud* ba poyon rasonida bud [1, p.26], *Dar vaqtho-i oxir* odat-i ba murda janosa xondan va ū-ro gūrondan ham barham xūrd [1, p.112].

In certain set of phrases and compositions, the derivative adverb formed by dint of the suffix *-ly* does not differ from simple one, as follows: to sell cheap / cheaply – arzon furūxtan; to speak loud / loudly – baland gap zadan; to go slow / slowly – ohista roh raftan; to come quick / quickly – *zud* omadan; to contact somebody direct / directly – bevosita bo kas-e dar aloqa budan

[13]: - “Xar hamon xar ast, polonaš digar šudaast,” – guft yake az bozoriyon qadr-e ovoz-i xud-ro *baland karda* [1, p.63].

It is worth mentioning that the usage of simple adverbs (without the adverbial suffix -ly) is characteristic only in oral speech or vernaculars. As a rule, such kinds of derivative adverbs are placed before the verb in a sentence: He quickly (quick – is wrong) ran towards the door. – *Ū tez ba nazd-i dar davida raft.*

It is worth mentioning that certain simple English adverbs are used without the adverbial suffix -ly and they are seen only in the composition of set of phrases:

“Take it easy! – *Xavotir našaved!*; Hold tight! – *Xud-ro mahkam dored!*; He held her close. – *Vay ū-ro saxt dar oğūš girift.*; Stay (Keep) clear of him! – *Az vay xuddori kuned!*; I always play (fight) fair. – *Man hameša az rū-i alodalt bozi mekunam*; Wipe the table clean. – *Miz-ro toza kun*; Feel free to ask questions. – *Az pursiš-i savol šarm nador*” [13].

CONCLUSION

Adducing the results of the conducted analysis concerned with the theme explored one can come to the conclusion that the majority of English adverbs are derivated by virtue of the adverbial suffix -ly. Contently, the formation of adverbs from different parts of speech is considered to be one of the main and most productive ways of adverb derivation or word-building in the comparative languages. We can confidently express our opinion that the usage of parts of speech in adverb derivation is not identical in Tajik and English languages. Adjectives are more frequently used in the formation of adverbs than other parts of speech in the languages being compared. Hereby, we can canvass those TEs of EDAs derived by the suffix -ly are not identical and the same-formed ones, and some of them are used and translated as STAs (simple Tajik adverbs), DTAs (derivative Tajik adverbs), CTAs (compound Tajik adverbs) & ComTAs (composite Tajik adverbs).

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